

Arrangements and Pressure in Statistical Mechanics

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Arrangements in statistical mechanics usually represent possible distributions of a quantity among N particles such that some constraint, such as average energy equaling a fixed value, holds. Calculations of the number of possible arrangements is useful because they may be used to determine probability. Arrangement calculations, however, usually assume the removal of some information and so we argue that they shed light on the dynamics of collisions in a system.

We consider two examples. The first is the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for which one has a large number N of particles and distributes energy E among these particles. Each distribution of particles is assumed to carry the same weight, i.e. a global approach is taken. One may then maximize the \ln of the number of arrangements subject to the constraint of a fixed average energy. This approach removes all possible information except that associated with an average energy and leads to a specific collision picture, namely $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$. In such a case, maximization is performed over all particles.

A second example is to consider N particles with total energy E , but to consider maximization for the first particle, i.e. it may have any energy from 0 to E with equal probability. The second particle may then have any energy from 0 to $E-e_1$, again with equal probability etc. In this example, there is a correlation and so all information is not removed. We suggest that such a scenario should give rise to a collision scheme which differs from that of an MB gas. We suggest that one may estimate the effects by considering the scenario in which one particle with energy e splits into two particles with energies e_1 and e_2 while two other particles combine to form a single particle. This should lead to no overall change in the system, so the probabilities for e_1 and e_2 seem to be governed by the probability scheme of the two particles which combine. In other words, one cannot suggest that e may break into any e_1, e_2 such that $e_1+e_2=e$ with equal probability.

Arrangements and Dynamics

The usual manner of treating a classical gas is that of Maxwell-Boltzmann. It seems to be completely general, but we argue that it is based on specific conditions:

- A. A total energy of E is distributed among N particles such that each distribution scheme carries the same weight.
- B. Particles are independent so that there exists a $P(e_i)$ independent of N such that the probability to find e_1 and e_2 together is $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$.

Two features of this approach for large N are that it considers distributions of all N particles as carrying the same weight and that each particle is independent. In particular, one performs a global maximization of the \ln of the number of arrangements subject to a constraint of a fixed average energy.

$$\ln(N! / \prod_i n_i!) + \sum_i e_i P(e_i) \quad ((1))$$

This describes a very specific dynamics of collisions because N does not appear in $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$ with $P(e_i)$ being unnormalized, i.e.. $P(e_i)=\exp(-e_i/T)$.

It is possible, however, to calculate the number of arrangements and hence probability using different distribution rules.

Non-global Maximization

The Maxwell-Boltzmann approach uses global maximization, i.e. it considers distributions of all N particles as having equal weight. In other words, there is no a priori correlation built in. By maximizing for large N subject to an average energy constraint, one obtains independent particle probabilities.

It is possible, however, to consider equal weight for energy for a single particle and then correlate this to the second particle etc. Such an approach leads to a different set of arrangements and hence probabilities. In particular, the first particle has equal probability to have energy e between 0 and E. This is an equal weight idea applied to a single particle. The second particle also has an equal weight principle, but its energy is constrained between 0 and E-e etc.

One may then calculate the number of arrangements for N=3 using:

$$\int_0^{E-e} de_1 = (E-e) \quad ((2))$$

For four particles, one has $\int_0^{E-e} de_1 \int_0^{E-e-e_1} de_2 = .5 (E-e)^2$

Thus, it seems one has an $(E-e)^{N-2}$ ((3)) probability result.

One immediately sees that ((3)) is dependent on N unlike the Maxwell-Boltzmann result. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$, where P is unnormalized, but one has two particles on the LHS and one on the RHS. For ((3)), imagine that two particles combine such that their energy is e. Then, the probability is $(E-e)^{N-1-2}$ while the original probability for e is $(E-e)^{N-2}$. In other words, there is an extra (E-e) factor present.

We suggest that this implies a different kind of collision dynamics than that of the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. One may note that in the large N limit:

$$(E-e)^{N-2} = E \exp(-e/(E/N)) \quad ((4))$$

In other words, N combines with E total and so appears to disappear. For non large N values, we suggest that one consider one particle with energy e splitting into e1 and e2 while two other particles combine to become one particle. As an example, one may choose N=3. At first, one might think that all e1,e2 combinations such that e1+e2=e have equal probability. This however,

is the global maximization scheme of the Maxwell-Boltzmann approach. It does not apply to the scheme of ((3)). Thus, what might seem like intuition is really based on what information can or cannot be removed. In the scheme of ((3)), one does not have a scenario in which a particle with e splits into all e_1, e_2 pairs with equal probability. Rather it must split so as to compensate for the probability loss when the other two particles combine. We suggest that this has consequences on collision dynamics.

Quantum Mechanics

As an aside, we consider another system in which one does use the global maximization approach of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, namely that of a quantum bound state. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle with momentum p represents maximum Shannon's entropy subject to an $ipx P(x)$ constraint. In other words, one considers a single particle with p . In a bound state, one combines these various $\exp(ipx)$'s such that energy is conserved i.e.

$$\left(\sum_{p} a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((5))$$

In other words, there is no global maximization here either.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that arrangements may be used to compute probabilities, but that direct assumptions regarding information lost are made and one must be aware of these. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one considers global maximization in that every full distribution of N particles has equal weight. In other words, particles in each distribution are on the same footing. This is not the only approach available. One may apply a loss of information to a single particle and then correlate particles. For example, one may have a single particle have any energy between 0 and E with equal probability. The second particle may then have equal probability to have any energy between 0 and $E-e$ etc. In such a case, one particle constrains the next, even though there is equal probability to have any energy in the allotted amount. This leads to a probability scheme of $(E-e)^{\text{power}(N-2)}$. In the large N limit, this is of the same form as the Maxwell-Boltzmann result, but otherwise is N dependent, showing that more information is present than in MB case. We suggest that this has an effect on dynamics because collisions must create this distribution. In particular, we suggest that one consider a single particle with energy e breaking into e_1 and e_2 . Using MB thinking, one might consider equal probability for all e_1, e_2 pairs such that $e_1 + e_2 = e$, but that would not create the $(E-e)^{\text{power}(N-2)}$ distribution. Thus, we suggest that collision dynamics must be different.